

Characterisation Data Enhanced Virtual Laboratory

Characterisation has become a capability where informatics infrastructure, expertise and best practice is essential to turning data into new discoveries.

To better enable research through characterisation, this project:

- Provides rich online environments for characterisation in the cloud and on high performance computing (HPC) platforms for specific areas;
- Extends data processing workflows to cover a broader range of instruments;
- Developed a national network of characterisation informatics fellows with expertise in research software engineering and related skills;
- Produced of a national training network and program of work to uplift data skills across characterisation users; and
- Continued operations of and improvements to the CVL desktop and associated middleware.

Start date

12 December 2017

Expected completion date

30 September 2019

Investment by ARDC

\$625,000

Co-investment partners

[Microscopy Australia](#)

[Australian Nuclear Science & Technology Organisation](#)

[\(ANSTO\)](#)

[Monash University](#)

[National Imaging Facility \(NIF\)](#)

[University of Sydney](#)

[University of Queensland](#)

[University of Western Australia](#)

[University of Wollongong](#)

Lead node

MONASH
University

2. Cryo-EM

By the end of 2018, there were 4-5 new cryo electron microscopes in Australia. Each of these microscopes are capable of producing 1-5 terabytes (TB) of data per day, which makes data management, storage and analysis challenging. This milestone will implement tools for the optimisation of initial processing parameters of the data from the microscopes, maximising usage and increasing the value from the instruments. It will explore data management and implement a prototype for the large CryoEM datasets that are of a scale which challenges previous work.

4. Neutron Techniques

ANSTO provides neutron and synchrotron beamlines for domestic and international researchers representing a broad range of disciplines. ANSTO curates data for thousands of experiments, with petabytes (PB) of data in millions of files. This milestone will improve the efficiency of the curation process and improve the user experience leading to higher productivity.

6. Training

This includes design and delivery of dedicated CVL training for trainers and users.

1. Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (CVL) Desktop

Continue operations of and improvements to the CVL Desktop and associated middleware that is used to process, analyse and visualise data from across 50+ Australian instruments, over four major HPC facilities, and underpins 2,000+ Australian researchers.

3. Electron Microscopy

Electron microscopy users are a significant community across Australia, supporting thousands of researchers across materials, life sciences, engineering, and other areas. This milestone will extend the electron microscopy workbench with tools informed by the AMMRF (now Microscopy Australia) tools survey. It will work toward a Trusted Data Repository and prototype a Windows CVL desktop with a selection of tools.

5. A network of informatics fellows established

A community of informatics fellows, experts and scientists will be established to help support the wider Characterisation community.

Core features

A National Characterisation Data Capability

Includes infrastructure (data management and data analysis), and expertise in informatics relating to characterisation.

Domain-focused Characterisation Data Projects

Focus areas that will uplift specific data-driven areas of need, will demonstrate the application of the broader DeVL in an exemplar field, and will apply existing infrastructure and best practise.

Who is this project for?

Researchers who make use of national and local characterisation facilities.

What does this project enable?

- Rich online environments for characterisation in the cloud and on HPC platforms for specific areas; Extending data processing workflows to cover a broader range of instruments.
- Development of a national network of characterisation informatics experts with expertise in research software engineering and related skills.
- Production of a national training network and program of work to uplift data skills across characterisation users.
- Continue operations of and improvements to the CVL desktop and associated middleware.

Handy resources

- Access the [Characterisation Virtual Laboratory \(CVL\)](#)

<p>Monash University</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>University of Queensland</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>University of Wollongong</p> <p>VISIT</p>		

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